

TECHNOLOGY OF USING CREATIVE ACTIVITY FOR FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHER'S PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This article will define and scientifically concretize the theoretical foundations of training future teachers of English in the preparation of future teachers of English; developed a methodological set of problems of practical solutions to problems of mastering difficulties in the study of various problems that arise when using innovative technologies in the educational process; Psychological problems that arise during the training of future English language teachers with the help of new innovative technologies, theoretical and scientific-methodological justification, generalization in practice, and preparation of methodological and scientifically based recommendations are also considered.

However, there is no concrete evidence of how these teachers use technology in their actual classrooms. In general, the use of technology in teaching was limited and depended on other factors such as teachers' readiness to learn, student participation, and frequent interaction and collaboration. This suggests a need for future research to explore the creative pedagogy of technology use in the classroom in order to contribute to the improvement of classroom practices related to creativity and technology use.

Keywords: innovative technology, information technology, new technology, independent work, research work, creative activity, Internet, and distance learning.

Introduction

Technology is defined as the rational craft or skill of producing something or achieving a goal that allows for creativity. This concept of technology is frequently associated with the concept of creativity, which defines creativity as the ability to act and perform in a specific manner in order to achieve a goal. Although the concept of creativity is still undefined, most people can recognize creative acts or behaviors when they see them. The difficulty in defining this concept arises from the fact that the quality of creativity is presented in various ways, and creativity also has different connotations depending on the context in which it is viewed. In this paper, we use the 'democratic' definition of creativity and the 'little c creativity' or LCC definition to identify teachers' creativity in the use of technology in teaching. These two concepts of creativity are more relevant because they regard creativity as a natural ability that all people possess. Based on these two concepts, every EFL teacher has the ability to be creative in their area of relevant knowledge and skills, including technology creativity [1].

The rapid development of technology has posed a challenge for classroom integration, which supports the concept of creativity as a process for constructing everyday creativity. Referring back to the two concepts of creativity used in this study, teachers have the opportunity to construct everyday creativity through the use of technology in their teaching practice. Technology does not generate ideas; rather, it can supplement skills by allowing for experimentation and exploration [2].

Materials and types of research

The objectives of this study are: firstly, to determine what features English language teachers use for innovative technologies, secondly, what are the advantages and disadvantages of using them in a creative approach to their implementation, and thirdly, to study the opinions of teachers. Students learn English with the help of innovative technologies. The method used in this study consists of qualitative and quantitative methods. The study aims to understand and explain

English teachers and their pedagogy, including the involvement of English teachers. Possible perspectives of English language teachers on the integration of creative innovation in English language teaching. The opinions and suggestions of students were taken into account.

Research questions

Below are the three research questions that guide this study:

1. What functions of the teacher are used in the innovative technology of teaching English at school?
2. What are the advantages and disadvantages of using innovative technology in language teaching in primary educational organizations?
3. What do students think about learning English with the help of new technology?

Participants

An exploratory mixed methods design was employed by interviewing 5 EFL teachers about the role of technology in teachers' creativity and administering a creativity questionnaire to 5 teachers.

Tools

The research we discussed here is a part of a larger study aimed at understanding teachers' beliefs about creativity in EFL classrooms including the characteristics of creative teachers, creative teaching practices, and the use of technology in teachers' creativity. In this article, we focus on the role of technology in developing teachers' creativity.

Second, 5 teachers from general education school №10 named after Ahmet Baitursynov were asked to fill out the questionnaire. Based on the general basis of the innovative model of inquiry education, we conducted a review and survey of its widespread instructions in modern domestic higher schools.

I presented 5 technologies of innovative teaching to the teachers and we started to determine which one is effective for each of them in the lesson, namely: problem-based learning, game technology, information technology, modular technology, contextual learning. These technologies help to study English effectively.

Third, participants were asked to select one of five options for frequency of technology use. Teachers were required to demonstrate the technology they often use in teaching. Most of the teachers said that they use the technology of games and information technology. He said that the rest of the technologies are often not implemented and pupils are not interested.

Because now it is impossible to surprise the children of the twenty-first century.

However, we started to create a comparison table of the innovative teaching model, analyzed the effectiveness and what results it gives to the students.

The statement in part can be reflected either in 'technology provides good teaching materials' or 'technology brings various issues from the online world into my classroom [3].

Procedure

Preparation of questionnaires and interviews

The questionnaire is based on the functional table of the new technology used. The validity of the survey and interview questions was reviewed for development and approval by the course consultants. Changes were made based on feedback from the above procedures. Both the questionnaires and interview questions were reviewed and approved by the course advisor prior to distribution.

Enter the survey

The questionnaires were physically distributed to the respondents. The questionnaire was used to find out what the respondents had done or were doing in the past with the use of mood. The first step in the analysis was to become familiar with the data by transcribing the interviews. This process allowed me to develop an initial understanding of the data. We then read the entire data set and assigned notes or codes to the statements.

The entries or codes refer to the content or meaning of the participants' statements, for example, we wrote "using technology for imaginative travel, technology facilitates the teaching and learning process, and being creative is not dependent on tools." This was a recursive process where we constantly moved back and forth between the entire data set. We followed a similar process for the 5 interview transcripts. I then compiled a "codebook" containing a coding list of the 5 interviews and grouped them into several categories. Some codes are grouped into one category if they have a similar meaning.

Interview

There were 5 teachers who used technologies in the training and were interviewed about their use, benefits and harms of the innovation. All interviews were digitally recorded and decoded, and both were translated into English for data analysis. The interview is designed to find out the opinions of the readers and the opinions of the participants.

According to the survey, an interview was conducted about the features of the use of innovative technology and the integration of the teacher's creativity. Accordingly, a questionnaire was used. Advantages and disadvantages of innovative technologies research questions. They were also asked to comment on benefits and regulations for those interested in using the innovative application.

Data analysis

Survey data were tabulated into a teaching innovation module to provide an overview of the role of technology in shaping teacher creativity and to generalize qualitative findings.

Research results

During the meetings and surveys, it was found that the teachers used a wide range of mechanical tools to explore their imaginations in the classroom, such as information technology, computers, projectors, tape recorders, the Internet, observational focus and note counting.

For teachers, information technology is very convenient in the process of distance education and it is very efficient and time-saving to communicate with the teacher anywhere, by phone, e-mail.

These innovations were divided into three categories: hardware, web, and audio-visual materials.

YouTube, Google, and social media use fall under the "Internet" category. And the "Audio-visual materials" category includes notes and PPTs. "Hardware" means computer, tablet, VCR and LCD projector. Survey data revealed that of all mechanical tools, it was the most common innovation used in the classroom. The web has become the most widespread innovation in distance learning. And audio-visual, presentation, podcast, video materials on YouTube have become very popular and effective[4].

This finding confirms the subjectivity of instructors' perceived use of the Internet in their inventiveness. However, they did not use the Internet directly in the classroom, instead they used the classroom environment to plan their learning. For this reason, the Internet becomes the smallest innovation used in the classroom. Any technological tools these instructors use will positively impact their mastery, audio-visual materials and equipment will help instructors effectively transform data. The web allows instructors to access additional materials for their inventive skills, such as videos of native speakers.

If we combine the new technology and the creative activity of the teacher, it includes: explanation, presentation of instructive films, discussion, work with instructional programs, free work with inventive writing; strategies of problem inquiry: heuristic discussion, conversation, questioning about the work, risk introduction of the instructional fabric, questioning about the work of the scientific research form, collective thinking-action of students in a small group; Regenerative strategies: performing appropriate tasks corresponding to the content and demonstration of the instructional material; creative-reproductive strategies: confusing words, creating fantasy works, changing trades, analyzing inventive situations, solving imaginary tasks; Forms of independent work of students: summarizing unique information, repeating innovative notes, referring to an inventive word, clarifying .

Strategies of conventional forms of learning: dynamic and middle way dynamic learning strategies are among the most common. We use different terms to describe entertainment models. "Fun", "imitation", "story about a real situation". Agreeing with the opinion of S. Abenbaeva, there is a place for imaginative innovations that are mostly unused in entertainment innovation. Therefore, at present, it has gained special power within the framework of instructional training [5].

Discussion

It was thought that teachers used a wide range of mechanical tools in their imagination, such as computer, universal telephone, web, LCD projector and notes, and that the repetition of this use may differ from one teacher to another. The implementation of these mechanical devices has various possibilities in the imagination of teachers. For visuals, the innovation brings their inventiveness to reality, making the exercises more realistic and providing instructional materials on various points. The web, interests, was the smallest common news used in the classroom. Although teachers acknowledged that the Internet made their imaginations a reality, they did not directly use the Internet in the classroom. They used the web as part of a facilitator leading to real classroom exercises. When some instructors conduct an introductory lesson on a "classroom discussion" or "virtual field trip," they use the Internet to research data in development and are familiar with how to view and coordinate what data they need for that movement. In these cases, the Internet makes data retrieval a real treat, and instructors can use exercises from the Web's existence.

Thus, the Internet plays an important role in shaping the imagination of teachers as a means of creating real situations and finding real data. Another important finding of this opinion is that all teachers used innovation in the classroom. They seem to consider the importance of innovation in their knowledge. Innovation has the potential to transform the minds of educators because it can open up untapped and authentic ways to be inventive with data innovation essentials, including provision, interactivity, power, speed, and programmed capabilities. It is clear that innovative technology and teacher's creativity will develop in creative ways. If a teacher has all these qualities, he can become a very qualified specialist [6].

The type of innovation that teachers think about depends on their needs and information about innovation, whether they refer to it for communication and discussion, or use it to create real situations. The emergence of thinking about it appears as a positive reaction to the use of innovation in the formation of creativity by teachers. They did not use the innovation as the most movement and the innovation may not change the information of the teachers. In any case, innovation does not seem to displace the work of the teacher, but innovation has made changes and stimulated teaching and learning with the educator as the most performing artist.

Innovation is not an "independent variable" that can be integrated into a framework to improve learning. Innovation does not give thought; innovation can complement abilities by giving meaning to experimentation and research [7].

Conclusion

Kazakhstan teachers do use technology in the classroom but they do not use it for online activities. For example, participating teachers use the Internet as part of their preparation process leading up to doing actual activities. These teachers seem to realize that being creative does not mean solely using the Internet in the classroom. There are other technological tools they can use to create creative activities such as hardware devices and audio-visual materials. With these tools,

these EFL teachers are still able to explore their creativity that and encourages learners' creativity. In this case, by using technology in their lesson planning, it helps transfer the teachers' creativity into reality, makes the activities more authentic, and provides teaching materials on various topics. However, the implementation of the technology will be meaningful or effective if the teachers know how to integrate technology into classroom activities. Also, the use of technology enables and encourages teachers to become more creative in their language teaching when there is a confluence of other variables such as teachers' willingness to learn, students' participation, frequent interaction and cooperation. Thus, technology cannot stand by itself to do the activities. The findings of this study have a number of important implications for future practice, especially for EFL teachers and researchers. First, this current study examined the role of technology in the development of teachers' creativity. The implementation of technology as described by teachers in this study provides examples of how EFL teachers could build their creativity through the use of technology in their practice. The findings revealed that teachers are aware of the importance of technology in creativity. However, there is no clear evidence about how these teachers use technology in their actual classrooms. Thus, future research need to investigate the creative pedagogy of technology use in the classroom by doing classroom observations, and identify how the teachers integrate technology into creative classroom activities.

Currently, there are several types of lectures: introductory, informational, review, problem-learning, visual, binary, pre-planned with errors, conference, meeting, "brainstorming" lecture or "group discussion lecture". The seminar is one of the main types of practical training sessions. The peculiarity of the seminar is the collective discussion of reports, abstracts, reports prepared by students under the guidance of teachers.

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